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**A STUDY ON “OUT- OF- HOME ADVERTISING” AND IT’S IMPACT ON BUYING
BEHAVIOUR OF CUSTOMERS- WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
PALAYAMKOTTAI REGION**

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ABSTRACT

Out-of-home (OOH) advertising or outdoor advertising is the advertising that reaches the consumers while they are at outside of their homes. Out-of-home media advertising is paying attention on marketing to consumers when they are "on the go" in public places. The purpose of this study is to discuss the effects and scope of outdoor advertisements which, by utilizing outdoor areas and social-spaces most commonly used by consumers, occupy an indispensable place with their size and visual impact and to measure the effectiveness of outdoor advertisements in influencing the purchasing behavior of consumers. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. The questionnaire is circulated among 125 respondents and 116 were collected back and 9 were found incomplete. So the sample size is restricted to 107. Simple random sampling method was adopted. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method, chi square and t test techniques are used in this study. It is concluded that Outdoor advertisements are the only advertisement tools to which the consumers are exposed without paying any charge and which have a significant persuade on purchasing behavior of the consumers and their visual effectiveness.

KEY WORDS: Out of home advertising, reasons, awareness, perception, impact on buying behavior,

INTRODUCTION

Now a day's companies are by means of various customs to attract customers headed for their product. For this reason they are using advertising, publicity, personal selling etc. among all marketing tools that advertisers decide to attract customers towards their products or the services offered, most important is out of home advertising. This is because its impact is comparatively long lasting relative to other marketing tools. In the modern world, technology enables us to exercise a level of creativity in outdoor advertising that would have been impossible only a few years ago, and there are more types of Out Of Home Media (OOHM) available now than ever before. OOH advertising formats fall into six main categories: billboards, street, roads, highways, transit, and alternative. Out of home advertising industry plays an important role in determining the economy of any country. Outdoor advertising is a very cost efficient way of putting across ones product to the general people. The sales record in the outdoor advertising market is predicted to go up in the near future. OOH advertisement is no more limited to billboards. With consumerism on an extraordinary rise, and more and more brands bombarding the Indian market, outdoor advertisement is all set to smash the jumble of advertisement in conventional mediums and fill in the gaps left by the other media.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mustafa Gulmez, Olgun kitapchi, Sukran karaca (2010) explains that people normally have optimistic opinions regarding outdoor advertisements. They assume that outdoor advertisements are more striking and imaginative when compared to other advertisement types and, their material size lends them an efficient visual impact.

Rizwana Iqbal, Sana Batool (2016) state in their study that billboards advertisement its rate to influence customers is higher relative to other media because it deliver information affordably, attract potential customer that all in turn enhances sales

Bianca, Simona, Alina Gabriela (2018), states that the we are living in a period of change, with new technology, social and demographic trends all pushing to modify our view of the world. Outdoor is a very visible medium that confers brands a presence on the street, in the reality of the consumer, but for this it must be renewed constantly. It costs nothing to the individuals, and it offers both value for time and money, by using dead time.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the reasons behind for watching out of home advertisement
- To understand awareness level among the respondents about out of home advertisement
- To find out the most preferable out of home advertising based on type of products
- To analyze the impact of out of home advertising in buying behavior of the respondents

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Outdoor advertisement methods are cost effective ways to promote a brand or service because outdoor advertisement one time investment. Outdoor advertisements have better impact of the consumer buying behavior. The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of outdoor advertisements on consumers who are living in Palayamkottai region and to measure the effects on respondent's buying behavior. The research also attempted to specify the different characteristics of outdoor advertisements and its impact on customers' purchase behaviors. Further this study can be conducted any other metropolitan cities also.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Every research has to face its limitations. Some are controllable and some are not controllable. The limitations of the study are as follows.

- The area of the study is restricted to Palayamkottai only
- It shall not cover any other domain except out of home advertising.
- Time available for the study is three month only ranging from Jan 2020 to March 2020.
- The sample size is restricted to 107.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study is a descriptive survey based study. It is mainly based on primary data and secondary data. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. The questionnaire is circulated among 126 respondents and 116 were collected back and 9 were found incomplete. So the sample size is restricted to 107. Simple random sampling method was adopted for selecting the respondents. The secondary data is collected through books, manuals and websites.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The statistical tools help us to evaluate the problems under the study in a judicial manner. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method, chi square and t test techniques are used in this study

DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1 : Demographic profile of the Respondents

Variables	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	70	65
	Female	37	35
Age	Below 20	4	04
	21 - 30 years	54	50
	31 - 40 years	22	21
	41 - 50 Years	16	15
	Above 50 years	11	10

Marital status	Married	65	61
	Unmarried	42	39
Educational Qualification	SSLC	17	16
	HSC	18	17
	UG	20	19
	PG	31	29
	Other Qualification	21	20
Occupation	Student	16	15
	Businessmen	25	23
	Profession	08	07
	Government employees	10	09
	Private employees	27	25
	Others	21	20
Monthly family income	Below -5,000	4	04
	5,001-10,000	26	24
	10,001-15,000	45	42
	15,001-20,000	08	07
	Above 20,000	24	22
Nature of family	Joint family	58	54
	Nuclear family	49	46
Exposure to out of home Advertising	All the times	56	52
	Sometimes	32	30
	Occasionally	19	18
	Never	0	0
Out of home ads results in change of attitude	Yes	67	62
	No	10	09
	May be	30	28

Purchased goods/ services under the influence of out of home advertisement	Yes	88	82
	No	19	18

Source:

Data collected through questionnaire

The above table explains that

- Majority (65%) of our respondents are male.
- Majority (50%) of our respondents are between the age group of 21 – 30 years.
- Majority (61%) of our respondents are married.
- Majority (29%) of our respondents have completed their UG degree.
- Majority (25%) of our respondents are private employees.
- Majority (42%) of our respondents have a monthly income of Rs 10000 to Rs 15000
- Majority (54%) of the respondents lives in joint family.
- Majority (52%) of our respondents say that they are exposed to out of home advertising all the time.
- Majority (62%) of the respondents say that out of home ads change their attitude.
- Majority (82%) of the respondent says that they purchase goods and services under the influence of out of home advertisement.

Table 2: Awareness among customers about out of home Advertising

Types of out of home advertising	Aware		Not aware	
	No of Respondents	% of Respondents	No of Respondents	% of respondents
Bill board advertising	60	56	47	44
Transit advertising	75	70	32	30
Digital advertising	96	89	11	11
Posters advertising	95	89	12	11
Banners advertising	98	92	09	08
Walls painting advertising	100	94	07	06

Source : Data collected through questionnaire

The above table explains about the respondent’s level of awareness about the out of home advertising. The result shows that majority of the respondents are aware about wall painting advertising, banner advertising, poster advertising and digital advertising than the bill board advertising and transit advertising.

Table 3: Reasons for watching out of home Advertising

Weighted average method is used to analyze the reasons to watch out of home advertising

Statement	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Total score	Avg Score	Rank
Visuals	225 (45)	172 (43)	21 (7)	18 (9)	3 (3)	439	4.1	I
Leisure travel	95 (19)	192 (48)	63 (21)	18 (9)	10 (10)	378	3.5	II
Effective design	65 (13)	108 (27)	93 (31)	34 (17)	19 (19)	319	2.98	V
Need based	45 (9)	96 (24)	81 (27)	54 (27)	20 (20)	296	2.8	VI
To get informed	85 (17)	116 (29)	63 (21)	44 (22)	18 (18)	326	3	IV
Color and contrast of the advertisement	115 (23)	128 (32)	75 (25)	24 (12)	15 (15)	357	3.3	III

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

From the above table it is inferred that majority of our respondents feel that they watch out of home advertising for its visual attractiveness followed by leisure travel and color and contrast of the out of home advertisement.

Table : 3 Most preferable out of home advertising based on type of products

Garrett ranking method is used to analyze the most preferable products among out of home advertising

FACTORS	SCORE	AVG. SCORE	RANK
Technology Products	5825	54.44	I
Furniture	5543	51.80	III
Education	5585	52.19	II
Food	5535	51.72	IV
Cosmetic and personnel care product	4685	43.78	VI
Health-Medical	4800	44.85	V

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

Above table :3 shows that six types of products are identified based on the reply from sample respondents and weighted average score is given. Technology product secured first rank , education secured second rank furniture product, secured third rank food product, secured fourth rank health and medical product secured fifth rank, cosmetic and personnel care product secured six rank.

Table no 4: Impact of out of home advertising in buying behavior of the respondents

S.NO	Particulars	Weighted Garrett score	Weighted average score	Rank
1.	Encourage purchase of a product	6258	58.48	I
2.	Cause immediate purchase	4545	42.47	VI
3.	Serve as a guide for product identification	5509	51.48	III
4.	Convince the consumer to purchase a product brand	5170	48.31	IV
5.	Promote interest in viewing the product	5745	53.69	II
6.	Damage the view of the place	4770	44.57	V

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

Above table : 4 shows the impact of out of home advertising. Majority of the respondents feel that out of home advertising encourages purchasing a product followed by promoting interest in viewing the product and serving as a guide for product identification.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H₀1: There is no association between the gender of respondents and the type of the outdoor advertisements they prefer to watch

Particulars	Calculated Value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	10.75	11.070	5	Accepted

Since the calculated value (10.75) is less than the table value (11.070) the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no association between gender and the type of the outdoor advertisements they prefer to watch.

H₀2: There is no association between the monthly income and their purchase of product under the influence of out of home advertising

Particulars	Calculated Value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	4	9.488	4	Accepted

Since the calculated value (4) is less than the table value (9.488) therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no association between monthly income and their purchase of product under the influence of out of home advertising.

H₀3: There is no significant difference between genders in their perceptions towards out of home advertising

	n	mean	Std deviation	Variance	Df	Significance	t stat	t critical two tail
Male	70	3.8	.97	0.94	77	0.05	3.37	+/- 2.0025
Female	37	3.2	.92	0.84				

Since the t value (3.37) does not lies between -2.0025 and +2.0025 we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore there is significant difference between male and female in their perception towards out of home advertising.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

Consumer will see outdoors advertising almost every day, although these days, it is harder & harder to actually grab the attention of the average customer. To grap the attention of the customer the advertiser makes sure the following elements are taken into account.

- ❖ Adequate spacing between letters & words
- ❖ Use a combination of capital & balanced berceuse letters to improve readability.
- ❖ Use the appropriate color and balanced typeface.
- ❖ Ensure 24/7 readability (this may mean lighting the advertisement at night).

To conclude, we are living in the age of transform, with new know-how, social and demographic trends all approaching to alter our view of the humanity. Outdoor is a very noticeable intermediate that confers brands a presence on the street, in the reality of the consumer, but for this it must be renewed constantly. It costs nothing to the individuals, and it offers both standards for time and money. In this respect, outdoor is a most favorable medium for the recent consumer. Out of home advertising should be in accord with environment, and always tidy and planned. Despite the budget, time, and credibility limitations of this work, new research paths could be exploited, on how outdoor advertising could adapt to the culture and personality of each specific metropolis. Outdoor medium in terms of advertisement and communication are coming to a very important phase all over the world. Outdoor advertisements are the only advertisement tools to which the consumers are exposed without paying any charge. Out of home advertising have an important pressure on purchasing actions of the consumers and encourages the purchase of products.

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